

Refractory Error and Ocular Biometry among Young Adults in Muzaffarpur, BiharSweta Kumari¹, Sushma Kumari², Rajiv Kumar Singh³¹Senior Resident, Department of Ophthalmology, Sri Krishna Medical College & Hospital, Muzaffarpur, Bihar, India.²Senior Resident, Department of Ophthalmology, Sri Krishna Medical College & Hospital, Muzaffarpur, Bihar, India.³Professor & Head, Department of Ophthalmology, Sri Krishna Medical College & Hospital, Muzaffarpur, Bihar, India.

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Abstract:**Objectives:** Refractive error is related to anatomic and functional differences in the eye, particularly in axial length, lens thickness, and lens opalescence. Myopia progression is more commonly produced by the increase of AL than for changes in the other optical components. In fact, the measurement of AL has been considered the most accurate way to monitor myopia progression. The present study was to evaluate the refractory error and ocular biometry among young adults in Muzaffarpur, Bihar.**Methods:** An ophthalmological examination was conducted with the assessment of visual acuity, the measurement of static refraction with the use of an autorefractor under cycloplegia, with prior administration of 0.5% proparacaine, followed by one application of 1% cyclopentolate eye drops, and two applications of 1% tropicamide, one drop each, with 5-minute intervals between drops. Biomicroscopic examination of the anterior segment was performed using a slit lamp, tonometry, cover test, corneal topography, and optical biometry.**Results:** A total of 100 adults with age group 18-30 years were enrolled. The mean age was 22.56±3.23 years. 42(42%) participants were males and 58(58%) were females. Regarding refractive errors, 12(12%) were hyperopic, 32(32%) were emmetropic, 51(51%) were myopic and 5(5%) were high myopic. Most of the patients of 18(18%) emmetropia had no family history. Most of the patients of 25(25%) myopia had history of one parent. 5(5%) patients of myopia had both parent history. 5% patients had not known the causes of refractory error. Most of the 34(34%) patients had >0 D Spherical equivalent OD. 31(31%) patients had -2.50 to 0 D. 28(28%) patients had -5.50 to -2.50 spherical equivalent OD.**Conclusions:** Myopia is the most common refractory error in young adult. Anterior segment biometric components and axial length make the greatest contribution to spherical equivalent in hyperopia and high myopia.**Keywords:** Refractory Error, Ocular Biometry, Young Adult.This is an Open Access article that uses a funding model which does not charge readers or their institutions for access and distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0>) and the Budapest Open Access Initiative (<http://www.budapestopenaccessinitiative.org/read>), which permit unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided original work is properly credited.**Introduction**

Refractive error is related to anatomic and functional differences in the eye, particularly in axial length, lens thickness, and lens opalescence [1,2].

Refractive error has a significant financial and practical impact on populations worldwide, and has potential to increase the risk of ocular disease, for example retinal detachment in myopic eyes and acute glaucoma in hyperopic eyes [3].

Myopia routinely develops in schoolchildren but may also appear in young people or adults [4]. The earlier myopia onsets, the greater will be the final myopic power expected in adulthood [5, 6]. Myopia progression is more commonly produced

by the increase of AL than for changes in the other optical components [7, 8]. In fact, the measurement of AL has been considered the most accurate way to monitor myopia progression [9].

In India, the prevalence of myopia among school children has shown a steady increase in the past decade from 4-8% to 14-21% [10, 11]. Accelerated eye growth is one of the key factors in the onset and progression of myopia. Hence, it is important to study the distribution of ocular biometry parameters among children to understand and predict myopia [12,13]. It is also important to have baseline ocular biometry data for individual ethnicity and race to understand the regional prevalence and patterns of myopia and to be able to

correlate and compare with other regions and ethnicities [14].

Patients with high myopia, and consequently, AL \geq 26 mm, have higher risks of decreased visual acuity in adulthood due to myopic maculopathy, retinal detachment and glaucoma [15, 16]. Although the growth of AL in the population from childhood to young age has been well studied, just a few studies have been reported in young adulthood [6, 7, 17]. Late adolescents are understood as the population between 17 and 19 years old, and young adults, between 20 and 24 years old, according to the World Health Organization [18]. Objectives of our study was to evaluate the refractory error and ocular biometry among young adults in Muzaffarpur, Bihar.

Material & Methods

The present study was conducted in the Department of Ophthalmology, Sri Krishna Medical College & Hospital, Muzaffarpur, Bihar during a period from July 2023 to October 2023. Data was collected with irrespective of sex by using the random sampling methods

Inclusion Criteria:

The selected subjects answered a questionnaire about outdoor activities, the history of their myopia onset, and parents' refractive history. All the participants with corrected visual acuity \geq 0.66 in both eyes and with a normal ophthalmologic examination, were included.

Exclusion Criteria:

Participants with associated ocular pathologies, with incomplete data, those who did not answer the questionnaire, those with astigmatism \geq 2 D or topographic irregular astigmatism, allergic to any

cycloplegic drug, patients with syndromes that interfere with the eye were excluded.

Methods:

A total of 100 young adults with age group 18 to 30 years were selected for the study. Subjects were evaluated at the ophthalmology OPD, SKMCH, Muzaffarpur, Bihar.

An ophthalmological examination was conducted with the assessment of visual acuity, the measurement of static refraction with the use of an autorefractor under cycloplegia, with prior administration of 0.5% proparacaine, followed by one application of 1% cyclopentolate eye drops, and two applications of 1% tropicamide, one drop each, with 5-minute intervals between drops. Biomicroscopic examination of the anterior segment was performed using a slit lamp, tonometry, cover test, corneal topography, and optical biometry. Lens power was measured indirectly with Bennett and Rozema's formula using the cycloplegic refraction, K1, K2, anterior chamber depth, lens thickness and AL [19].

Statistical Analysis

Data was analysed by using latest version of SPSS software. Mean and standard deviation were observed. P- value was taken less than or equal to 0.05 ($p \leq 0.05$) for significant differences.

Results

In the present study, a total of 100 adults with age group 18-30 years were enrolled. The mean age was 22.56 ± 3.23 years. 42(42%) participants were males and 58(58%) were females. Regarding refractive errors, 12(12%) were hyperopic, 32(32%) were emmetropic, 51(51%) were myopic and 5(5%) were high myopic. Mean of refractory error and ocular biometry was seen in table 1.

Table 1: Mean refractive and biometric data (\pm S.D.) for right eyes of all subjects.

Variables	Mean \pm S.D.
Age	22.56 \pm 3.23
Uncorrected visual acuity OD	0.42 \pm 0.35
Uncorrected visual acuity OS	0.66 \pm 0.31
Spherical equivalent OD	-1.83 \pm 2.56
Spherical equivalent OS	-1.89 \pm 2.83
Keratometry - K1	44.21 \pm 2.76
Keratometry - K2	45.72 \pm 2.12
Anterior chamber depth	4.21 \pm 0.31
Lens thickness	5.22 \pm 0.32
Axial length	26.75 \pm 2.72
Axial length emmetropic	24.68 \pm 0.92
Axial length myopic	26.74 \pm 1.24
Axial length high myopic	28.12 \pm 3.78
Axial length hyperopic	24.86 \pm 0.74
Lens power	24.12 \pm 2.10

In the present study, most of the patients of 18(18%) emmetropia had no family history. Most of the patients of 25(25%) myopia had history of one parent. Most of the 5(5%) patients of myopia had both parent history. 5% patients had not known the causes of refractory error.

Table 2: Distribution of spherical equivalent refraction for right eyes of all subjects.

Refractive group	No Family history	One parent	Both parent	Don't know	Total
Hyperopia	6(6%)	4(4%)	2(2%)	-	12(12%)
Emmetropia	18(18%)	7(7%)	4(4%)	3(3%)	32(32%)
Myopia	19(19%)	25(25%)	5(5%)	2(2%)	51(51%)
High myopia	1(1%)	3(3%)	1(1%)	-	5(5%)
Total	45(45%)	41(41%)	12(12%)	5(5%)	100(100%)

In the present study, most of the 34(34%) patients had >0 D Spherical equivalent OD. 31(31%) patients had -2.50 to 0 D. 28(28%) patients had -5.50 to -2.50 spherical equivalent OD.

Table 3: Distribution of refractive errors.

Spherical equivalent OD	Percentage
-10 to -7.50	1(1%)
-7.50 to -5.50	6(6%)
-5.50 to -2.50	28(28%)
-2.50 to 0	31(31%)
>0	34(34%)
Total	100(100%)

Discussions

Refractive error has a significant financial and practical impact on populations worldwide, and has potential to increase the risk of ocular disease, for example retinal detachment in myopic eyes and acute glaucoma in hyperopic eyes [3]. In some studies, part of refractive errors has been attributed to ocular biometrics [20,21]. Most reports suggest axial length (AL) and vitreous chamber depth (VCD), as the most important components in relation to refractive errors [22,23]. Studies on the association between refractive errors and ocular biometrics such as corneal power (CP), central corneal thickness (CCT), anterior chamber depth (ACD), and lens thickness (LT) are inconclusive. For example, Shufelt et al [24] and Mallen et al [21] reported a correlation between refractive errors and CP while McBrien et al [25] and Yekta et al [26] found no significant correlation between these two variables. Some studies have reported higher ACD readings in myopes and lower readings in hyperopes [21,27].

In the present study, 100 adults with age group 18-30 years were participated. The mean age was 22.56 ± 3.23 years. 42(42%) participants were males and 58(58%) were females. Regarding refractive errors, 12(12%) were hyperopic, 32(32%) were emmetropic, 51(51%) were myopic and 5(5%) were high myopic.

A study in 2002 from the Brazilian northeast population, considering the age group 16 years or more, found a myopia prevalence of 15.81% [28]. It is important to consider that the cut point for myopia was based on spherical power and not on spherical equivalent.

In the present study, most of the patients of 18(18%) emmetropia had no family history. 25(25%) myopia had history of one parent. 5(5%) patients of myopia had both parent history. 5% patients had not known the causes of refractory error. Mean axial length (AL) was 26.75 ± 2.72 mm. The standard value of AL of the human eye is internationally taken to be around 24 mm in adulthood regardless of sex or race, whereas AL tends to be longer in myopic and shorter in hypermetropic eyes comparing to that of emmetropic [29]. AL average values are variables in the literature. The mean AL observed in this paper is larger than those of Refs. [30, 31]. In which ultrasound, low-coherence reflectometry, and partial coherence interferometry are used, respectively. Conversely, Refs. [32, 33] using low-coherence reflectometry and partial coherence interferometry, respectively, show larger average values. Previous researches in Cuba report larger [34], much larger [36], shorter [35], and much shorter [36] average AL when compared with our results. It should be noted that the analyzed periods in all these works include only one year or less, and that the sample size is much smaller than ours, explaining the dispersion in their results. Specifically, in the case of Ref. [37], more than 93% of patients had myopic astigmatism while the result of Ref. [36] is in accordance with his study's design, where all the patients were hyperopes. Average ACD in our work (4.21 ± 0.31) is shallower than reported in Latino populations [38] and to a lesser extent, those of Refs. [39, 40] in Asian populations. On the other hand, Hashemi et al. [31] report an ACD average even shallower than ours using the biometer LENSTAR/BioGraph (WaveLight AG, Erlangen, Germany). Differences

between these two biometers may affect the comparative analysis since ACD value in Lenstar refers to the distance between corneal endothelium and lens anterior capsule while the distance for this variable in IOL Master is taken from corneal epithelium to lens anterior capsule. That is why Lenstar uses the sum of central pachymetry and ACD values for IOL calculation [35].

In the present study, mean lens thickness (LT) was 5.22 ± 0.32 mm. It was higher than that reported in studies that used an A-scan ultrasound, which has lower resolution than the SS-OCT, for studying Latino [38, 41] and elderly Chinese populations [42]. Hashemi et al. [31] and Ferreira et al. [32], using both low-coherence optical reflectometry (Lenstar) observed much smaller LT values. As far as we know, a previous report of this magnitude has not been published on Cuban patients. Keratometry average value and its distribution in our study are close to those observed in European population based studies using partial-coherence interferometry [43] and optical low-coherence reflectometry [32].

Cuban researchers [37, 45] using autorefractor-keratometers have previously reported slightly lower values. Keratometry measurements may vary when different evaluation methods are used, as it was demonstrated in Ref. [46] reporting a significantly lower corneal power when measurements were obtained with autorefractor-keratometers than those measured by IOL Master.

In the present study, most of the 34(34%) patients had >0 D Spherical equivalent OD. 31(31%) patients had -2.50 to 0 D. 28(28%) patients had -5.50 to -2.50 spherical equivalent OD. The World Health Organization – WHO - defines high myopia as <-5 D, however, currently, the International Myopia Institute - IMI – considers it to be <-6 D [47, 48].

In terms of biometric measurements, the two previously published population-based studies have found contradictory age-related differences [49, 2]. In Singapore, younger adult Chinese had longer axial lengths compared to older Chinese.¹⁰In contrast, in Mongolia, there was no age-related difference in axial length.¹¹ Similar to the Mongolians, in our study, no age-related differences in axial length were noted. One explanation for this is that once the eye has achieved its adult size, little change occurs in the axial length during adulthood and with aging.

Conclusions

The present study concluded that the myopia is the most common refractory error in young adult. Anterior segment biometric components and axial length make the greatest contribution to spherical equivalent in hyperopia and high myopia.

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